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Digital Literacy and Ethical Media Use: Role of Education in Combating Cyberbullying and Protecting Children's Privacy

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Abstract

The growth of digital platforms in India has led to a surge in cyberbullying, particularly among children, as they are vulnerable. With increasing access to the internet and social media, children face risks that extend beyond the physical world, including harassment, threats, and other forms of cyber abuse or cyberbullying. India leads the world in the frequency of cyberbullying, with over 33% of children reporting having been the victim of it. Based on data from the NCRB, there was a 63.48% increase in cybercrimes between 2018 and 2019. (National Crime Records Bureau [NCRB], 2020) With this research paper, the author intends to explore how schools, as formal agents of socialisation, can effectively integrate digital citizenship into curricula, adopt preventive legal education programs, and develop reporting and redressal mechanisms aligned with child protection laws. This paper also analyses some of the statutory frameworks with relevant precedents and assesses how existing legal standards intersect with pedagogical responsibilities. Furthermore, it investigates the importance of empowering teachers, parents, and students with knowledge of online rights, privacy laws, and safe digital practices, emphasising international best practices. Finally, this paper suggests that enhancing digital literacy in schools is not just

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educationally important but also a legal and ethical duty to protect children online. It calls for integrated reforms in policy, law, and education to help children safely navigate the digital world, uphold their privacy rights, and promote respectful online behaviour, making education a key defence against cyberbullying and digital harm.

Keywords: Cyberbullying, Privacy Rights, Cybercrime, Strategies, Prevention, social media

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1. Introduction

The expression “cyberbullying” was first introduced by Bill Belsey, a Canadian educator. It refers to a form of online harassment in which digital technologies are used to intimidate, threaten, or target an individual. Often described as online bullying, it represents a serious form of digital abuse capable of causing enduring emotional and psychological harm (V. Kapoor et al., 2024).

Under the framework of the Information Technology Act, 2000, cyberbullying may be understood as a cyber offence involving the misuse of information and communication technologies to damage a person’s reputation, mental well-being, or dignity. Such conduct typically results in adverse consequences for the victim. The National Crime Prevention Council characterises cyberbullying as the act of using the internet, mobile phones, or other digital devices to transmit or publish messages or images intended to harm or embarrass another individual (Shivangi Gautam et al., 2023). Due to its harmful nature, cyberbullying has become increasingly prevalent among children. Unlike traditional bullying, where a child may seek assistance from teachers or trusted adults, cyberbullying extends beyond physical spaces and continues across digital platforms. This persistent exposure is often exacerbated by the lack of effective supervision over social media and online interactions. Children are particularly susceptible because of limited awareness and digital literacy, leading to a growing number of reported cases across the country (Refai, S. A. et al., 2024).

A tragic illustration of its impact is the suicide of a medical student in Kerala, reportedly linked to a manipulated WhatsApp conversation among peers. While the precise causes behind cyberbullying vary, it is widely acknowledged that the anonymity offered by social media platforms emboldens perpetrators to engage in such harmful behaviour (V. Kapoor et al., 2024).

2. Objectives of The Paper:

- To understand the concept and meaning of cyberbullying.
- To identify the various forms and manifestations of cyberbullying.
- To examine the underlying causes contributing to cyberbullying.
- To develop awareness regarding preventive measures and strategies to address cyberbullying.

3. Research Methodology

The present study adopts a doctrinal and analytical research methodology. The research is primarily based on secondary sources of data, including statutes, judicial decisions, government reports, policy documents, journal articles, books, reports of

national and international organisations, and other relevant academic literature concerning cyberbullying, digital literacy, ethical media use, and children's privacy rights. The study undertakes a detailed examination of the existing legal framework governing cyberbullying and child protection in India, particularly the provisions of the Information Technology Act, 2000, the Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, 2012, the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023, the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023, and other relevant laws and policies. Judicial pronouncements of the Supreme Court of India, High Courts, and selected foreign jurisdictions have also been analysed to understand the evolving legal position concerning online harassment, privacy rights, and the protection of children in digital environments. In addition to legal analysis, the study employs an analytical and descriptive approach to examine the nature, forms, causes, and consequences of cyberbullying among children. Government publications, including reports of the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), policy documents issued by the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MeitY), and reports of child protection agencies, have been reviewed to assess the contemporary challenges posed by cyberbullying and online privacy violations.

The research further analyses the role of educational institutions in promoting digital literacy, ethical media use, and responsible digital citizenship. Comparative references to international practices and policy measures have been incorporated wherever relevant to identify effective strategies for preventing cyberbullying and safeguarding children's privacy rights.

The methodology is therefore qualitative in nature and seeks to critically evaluate the adequacy of existing legal and educational mechanisms while proposing reforms aimed at strengthening child protection, digital literacy, privacy safeguards, and cyberbullying prevention in India.

4. Characteristics of a Typical Bully (adapted from Ms. Pooja et al., 2023)

- i. They tend to assert dominance and prefer controlling others.
- ii. They often achieve their goals by manipulating or exploiting people around them.
- iii. They struggle to understand or empathise with the viewpoints of others.
- iv. Their personal desires and emotions are prioritised over the rights and needs of others.
- v. In the absence of parental or authoritative supervision, they may harm other children.
- vi. They project their own insecurities onto victims, frequently blaming them and making unfounded allegations.
- vii. They avoid accepting responsibility for their actions.
- viii. They fail to foresee or consider the consequences of their behaviour.
- ix. They constantly seek attention and validation.
- x. They hold contempt for their victims, perceiving them as inferior, insignificant, and undeserving of respect.

5. Forms of Cyberbullying

Cyberbullying can generally be classified into ten primary categories, and those are as follows:

5.1. Omission or Exclusion When someone is excluded, they might lose their social media group membership and become the target of trolling. Bullies attempt to disseminate false information about the victim. (Kaur, M. et al., 2022)

5.2. Harassment: This type of cyberbullying involves the use of offensive language or behaviour based on technological issues, which can leave the victim feeling anxious, scared, or sad. (Iyer, C. et al., 2021)

- Disseminating false information, making fun of, or insulting other people; harassing someone due to their colour, religion, sexual orientation, handicap, or gender identity
- Attempting to get retribution or purposefully humiliating someone online;
- Engaging in inappropriate sexual conduct through text messages, emails, or other digital and social media platforms; this also includes the misuse or distribution of another individual's private images or recordings.

5.3. Outing/doxing: Outing, often called doxing, is a kind of cyberbullying in the context of cybercrime. Doxing is a crime in which someone's name, private information, or private communications are disseminated without that person's permission. (Jaya Thapa, 2024)

5.4. Trickery: This form of bullying is similar to "outing"; however, rather than immediately revealing the victim's secrets with harmful intent, the perpetrator initially gains the victim's confidence and trust before misusing that information.

5.5. Cyberstalking: When someone engages in cyberbullying, the bully follows their victim around the internet for an extended period of time, stalking them before attempting to torment them. (Zhu, C. et al., 2021)

5.6. Frapping: By uploading negative stuff about the victim, the bullies utilise the victim's account to discredit the victim.

5.7. Masquerading/impersonation: Instead of gaining access to the target's account in this instance, the cyberbullies create an account in their name and use it to carry out nefarious activities.

5.8. Dissing: The perpetrator undermines the victim's reputation by spreading false rumours or sharing deceptive information. They may contact the victim's friends privately or post derogatory content on social media to damage the victim's image.

5.9. Trolling or Angling: When someone is being trolled, they may receive a lot of comments on their post, which may cause them to feel offended and upset. It can be frightening if someone is the target of criticism or ridicule for their behaviour.

5.10. Flaming: Roasting, or flaming, is a type of cyberbullying in which a victim is harassed online or in groups using offensive words.

6. Effects of Cyber Bullying

The effects experienced by victims are profoundly harmful, particularly in relation to their social well-being, emotional stability, and overall quality of life. Despite the seriousness of the issue, responses from educational institutions and peer groups are often inadequate, inconsistent, or entirely lacking, thereby failing to provide meaningful protection or support. At the same time, the extent and intensity of harm suffered by victims are not uniform; they are shaped by a range of contextual elements, including the degree of anonymity enjoyed by the perpetrator and the presence or absence of bystanders. For example, in many instances of cyberbullying, victims face an added layer of psychological distress because they are unable to identify the source of the harassment. This uncertainty fosters a persistent sense of suspicion and insecurity, as victims may begin to perceive anyone within their social or digital circle as a potential aggressor (Pallathadka, H. et al., 2021).

In addition, cyberbullying differs significantly from traditional bullying in its scope, persistence, and impact. Digital platforms enable harmful content to be shared instantaneously and repeatedly, often reaching a vast and undefined audience. As a result, victims frequently feel exposed, scrutinised, and powerless, as if their humiliation is being continuously witnessed by others. This "always-on" nature of

online harassment removes the possibility of safe spaces, making it difficult for victims to disengage or recover. The involvement of passive or active bystanders can further intensify the harm, as silence or participation may reinforce the bully's behaviour and deepen the victim's sense of isolation.

Consequently, cyberbullying constitutes a serious psychological and social concern. Its repercussions may extend beyond immediate emotional distress to include long-term mental health challenges such as chronic anxiety, depression, loss of self-esteem, social withdrawal, and even impaired academic or professional functioning. The cumulative impact underscores the urgent need for more effective institutional interventions, awareness mechanisms, and supportive frameworks to address and mitigate the harms associated with cyberbullying (Pathak, V. K. et al., 2024).

7. Effects of Cyberspace on Children

Children's interactions with cyberspace are multifaceted, involving both positive and negative outcomes. Children are exposed to a range of hazards and problems when using the Internet, even though it provides a wealth of educational, social, and entertainment opportunities. (Raj, A., 2024) The following are some salient features of children's exposure to cyberspace:

7.1 Positive Impact

7.1.1. Access to Information and Education: Children can access educational materials, online courses, and academic resources thanks to the abundance of resources and information available to them in cyberspace. This promotes academic success and allows for self-directed learning. (Sharma, S., 2023)

7.1.2. Social Connectivity: Through social media sites, messaging applications, and online forums, kids may communicate with classmates, family members, and communities across the world. This promotes cultural interchange, friendships, and social contact, which advances social development and a sense of belonging. (Mr. S. Tripathi et al, 2011)

7.1.3. Creativity and Expression: Children may express themselves artistically through writing, music, painting, and other digital content production on online platforms. They may showcase their skills, viewpoints, and ideas to a large audience, which boosts creativity and self-assurance.

7.1.4. Entertainment and Recreation: There are several entertainment possibilities available in cyberspace, such as digital media material, streaming services, and online games. These pursuits offer chances for leisure and recreation as well as relaxation and enjoyment.

7.1.5. Learning and Skill Development: Children may enhance their critical thinking, problem-solving, and digital literacy abilities by engaging in interactive educational games, simulations, and virtual learning environments. They may study STEM subjects, programming, and coding in fun and interactive ways.

7.2 Negative Impact

7.2.1. Cyberbullying and Harassment: Children are particularly susceptible to cyberbullying, trolling, and various forms of online abuse, which can significantly undermine their mental and emotional health. Negative experiences on messaging platforms and social networking sites often expose them to humiliation, threats, or persistent harassment, leading to serious psychological consequences. Such interactions may trigger anxiety, depression, emotional distress, and diminished self-confidence. As noted by B. S. Shivashankar et al. (2018), the pervasive and often anonymous nature of digital platforms intensifies the impact of such behaviour, making it difficult for children to escape or seek timely support. The continuous exposure to harmful content and hostile communication can also impair their social

development, academic performance, and overall sense of security in online environments.

7.2.2. Exposure to Inappropriate Content: Children frequently encounter harmful online content, including violent material, sexually explicit imagery, hate speech, and other forms of age-inappropriate information (Dr. Samir Bhadury, 2022). Such exposure can have serious consequences for their overall development. It may distort their understanding of social norms and relationships, gradually desensitise them to aggression or explicit behaviour, and blur the distinction between acceptable and unacceptable conduct. Prolonged interaction with this kind of content can also adversely affect children's mental and emotional well-being. It may lead to anxiety, fear, confusion, or the normalisation of harmful attitudes and behaviours. In some cases, children may begin to imitate what they observe or develop skewed perceptions about violence and sexuality. As noted by Mr. Rahul et al. (2002), continuous exposure to such material can weaken emotional responsiveness and impair healthy psychological growth, ultimately placing children at risk of long-term cognitive and behavioural challenges.

7.2.3. Privacy and Security Risks: Unintentionally disclosing personal information online by kids can result in identity theft, privacy violations, and cyberstalking. Their digital security and safety might be jeopardised by harmful software, phishing attempts, or online fraud. (S. Mittal et al., 2024)

7.2.4. Addiction and Screen Time: Overuse of screens and the internet can lead to sedentary behaviour, addiction, and sleep disorders in kids. Their academic performance, social interactions, and physical health may all be impacted by excessive internet use.

7.2.5. Online Predators and Grooming: Online predators who groom and use deceitful techniques to exploit children for sex are a potential threat to children. This puts their safety and well-being in danger of cases of online sexual abuse, sextortion, or trafficking.

7.2.6. Digital Divide: Children from diverse socioeconomic origins have a digital gap due to differences in internet access, digital literacy, and technology resources. Children who don't have access to the Internet may experience disadvantages in their social inclusion, education, and opportunities. (Garnefski, N. et al, 2014)

All things considered, although children can benefit much from the internet, there are also serious hazards and problems involved. Talking about the increasing daily cybercrimes becomes crucial.

8. Laws Regarding Cyberbullying in India

8.1 IT Act, 2000

The Information Technology Act, 2000 (as amended in 2008) was enacted with the primary objective of granting legal recognition to electronic data, digital transactions, and communications exchanged through electronic means. It provides a comprehensive legal framework to regulate cyber activities and address offences committed in the digital environment. Under the Act, various cyber offences such as hacking, identity theft, cheating by impersonation, and violation of privacy are punishable with imprisonment ranging from three to five years, a fine that may extend to one lakh rupees, or both. In more serious or aggravated circumstances, the penalties may be significantly higher depending on the nature and gravity of the offence. With specific reference to online misconduct, individuals engaging in abusive, fraudulent, or derogatory behaviour through social media platforms, the internet, or other forms of digital communication may be held liable under several provisions of the Act. For instance, Sections 66A (now struck down but historically relevant), 66C (identity theft), 66D (cheating by personation using computer resources), and 66E (violation of privacy) have been invoked to address harmful

online conduct. Furthermore, Sections 67, 67A, and 67B of the Act deal with the publication or transmission of obscene, sexually explicit, or child-related exploitative content in electronic form. These provisions impose stringent punishments, reflecting the seriousness of offences involving the digital dissemination of inappropriate or harmful material. Overall, the Act plays a crucial role in safeguarding individuals against cyber harassment, protecting digital privacy, and maintaining accountability in the rapidly evolving online ecosystem (S. Batra, 2020).

8.2 Additional Legal Provisions Applicable to Cyberbullying (India)

A range of statutory provisions primarily under the Information Technology Act, 2000 and the Indian Penal Code can be invoked to address different forms of cyberbullying and online harassment. These are outlined and explained below:

Obscene electronic content (Section 67, IT Act): This provision penalises the publication or transmission of obscene material in electronic form. It is commonly applied in cases where individuals circulate vulgar or offensive digital content intended to harass or degrade others.

Sexually explicit material (Section 67A, IT Act): Section 67A deals with the sharing or transmission of content depicting sexually explicit acts through electronic means. It prescribes stricter punishment compared to general obscenity offences, reflecting the seriousness of such conduct.

Insult to a woman's modesty: This section criminalises any word, gesture, or act intended to insult the modesty of a woman. In the context of cyberbullying, it applies to offensive messages, comments, or posts targeting women's dignity.

Defamation through electronic communication: Sending emails or messages containing defamatory statements that harm a person's reputation can attract liability under this provision. Cyber defamation has become increasingly relevant with the rise of social media platforms.

Obscene or defamatory publication for circulation or blackmail: This provision addresses the publication, distribution, or advertisement of grossly indecent or defamatory content, especially when used as a means of coercion or blackmail in online settings.

Cyberstalking: Bharatiya Naya Sanhita, 2023, penalises the act of repeatedly following, contacting, or attempting to contact a woman despite clear disinterest. In digital spaces, this includes persistent messaging, monitoring online activity, or unwanted communication.

Sexual harassment: Making sexually coloured remarks, sending explicit messages, or engaging in other forms of unwelcome sexual conduct online falls within the ambit of this section.

Violation of privacy (Section 66E, IT Act): This section penalises the intentional capture, publication, or transmission of private images without consent, thereby protecting individuals against digital intrusions into their personal space.

Criminal intimidation by anonymous communication: This provision applies when threats or harassment are carried out through anonymous or concealed identities, a common feature in cyberbullying cases involving fake profiles or untraceable accounts.

Collectively, these provisions demonstrate that cyberbullying is not governed by a single, standalone law in India but is instead addressed through a combination of legal frameworks. The IT Act focuses on offences involving electronic data and digital platforms, while the IPC addresses broader criminal conduct such as defamation, harassment, and intimidation. This layered approach allows law enforcement agencies to respond effectively to the multifaceted nature of cyberbullying, ensuring both accountability and protection for victims in the digital sphere.

8.3 The Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, 2012 (POCSO Act 2012)

POCSO Act is a comprehensive legal framework enacted to safeguard individuals below the age of eighteen from sexual abuse, exploitation, harassment, and exposure to pornography. The Act was designed to address the gaps in existing laws by specifically recognising a wide range of sexual offences against children and ensuring their effective prosecution. It clearly defines and criminalises various forms of abuse, including penetrative and non-penetrative sexual assault, sexual harassment, and the use of children for pornographic purposes. Importantly, the Act is gender-neutral, thereby extending protection to all children irrespective of gender. It also acknowledges that such offences may occur both in physical settings and through digital or electronic platforms, making it relevant in the context of online exploitation and cybercrime. The POCSO Act further establishes child-friendly procedures for reporting, recording evidence, and conducting trials. It mandates that statements of child victims be taken in a safe and supportive environment, often in the presence of parents or trusted individuals, and ensures that the identity of the child is kept confidential. Special courts are designated for the speedy trial of such cases, and stringent punishments are prescribed to deter offenders. Additionally, the Act places a legal obligation on individuals, including parents, teachers, and institutions, to report suspected cases of child abuse, thereby strengthening accountability and early intervention mechanisms. Overall, the POCSO Act plays a crucial role in protecting children from sexual offences, ensuring justice, and promoting a safer environment both offline and online.

8.4 National Cyber Security Policy-2013

Multiple objectives guided the Indian government's implementation of national cyber security. One of the policy's objectives is to prevent and properly investigate cybercrimes, particularly those directed against minors. It provides an appropriate legal framework to enhance enforcement capabilities. Its objective is to increase public knowledge of cybersecurity. In addition, the measure protects citizens' data, prohibits privacy violations, and protects them against financial losses resulting from cybercrimes, such as data theft caused by privacy violations.

8.5 The Digital Personal Data Protection Act of 2023

To guarantee the preservation of children's privacy, the Act offers several safeguards. One of the most important clauses is that consent must be granted by the age of 18. The Act mandates that before processing a child's data, a data fiduciary must get consent from the guardians. It also recommends that data fiduciaries who only work with children register with the data protection authorities on an obligatory basis. One qualifying factor for designating a large data fiduciary is the processing of children's data and the provision of services to them. Legislation outlines additional duties that apply to fiduciaries of significant data. It is illegal for data fiduciaries to track or keep an eye on children's data or handle personal information in a way that might put minors at risk.

9. Children's Privacy Rights In India's Digital Landscape

9.1 Right to Privacy under the Indian Constitution

In the landmark judgment of Justice K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India (2017), the Supreme Court of India unequivocally affirmed that the right to privacy is a fundamental right protected under Article 21 of the Constitution. The Court interpreted this right broadly to include informational and digital privacy, thereby extending constitutional safeguards to individuals in online environments and digital interactions. This recognition marked a significant development in Indian constitutional jurisprudence, especially in the context of rapid technological

advancement and increasing reliance on digital platforms. The ruling underscores that individuals have a legitimate expectation of privacy over their personal data, communications, and online activities. Consequently, any intrusion into such privacy must satisfy the tests of legality, necessity, and proportionality. This framework has become central to evaluating state actions and regulatory measures concerning surveillance, data protection, and cyber governance. However, the application of this principle becomes complex when it comes to children and adolescents in digital spaces. While minors are entitled to the same fundamental right to privacy, concerns arise regarding the need for supervision by parents, guardians, or authorities to protect them from risks such as cyberbullying, online exploitation, and harmful content. This creates an ongoing tension between ensuring a child's autonomy and safeguarding their well-being. Scholars, including N. S. Khudhair (2021), highlight that the challenge lies in striking a careful balance between these competing interests. Excessive monitoring may infringe upon a child's privacy and autonomy, whereas insufficient oversight may expose them to serious online harms. Therefore, there is a growing need for nuanced legal and policy frameworks that both respect children's privacy rights and enable reasonable, proportionate intervention to ensure their safety in digital environments.

9.2 Personal Data Protection Bill, 2019 (and the current legal position in India)

The proposed **Personal Data Protection Bill, 2019**, was designed to establish a comprehensive framework for regulating the collection, storage, and processing of personal data in India. A key feature of the Bill was its emphasis on safeguarding children's data. It mandated that entities handling data must obtain verifiable parental consent before processing the personal information of individuals below 18 years of age. This provision was particularly significant in addressing risks such as cyberbullying, online exploitation, and privacy breaches involving minors, as it imposed a higher standard of responsibility on digital platforms and service providers. However, the 2019 Bill was not enacted in its original form. Instead, India introduced the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023, which now constitutes the primary legal framework governing data protection. This legislation retains the core objective of protecting personal data while simplifying compliance structures. Importantly, it continues to recognize children as a sensitive category of data subjects. Under the Act, companies (referred to as "data fiduciaries") must obtain verifiable parental consent before processing the data of children, and they are prohibited from engaging in tracking, behavioural monitoring, or targeted advertising directed at minors if such activities are likely to cause harm. From a contemporary legal standpoint, these provisions play a crucial role in combating cyberbullying and online harassment. By restricting unauthorised data use and ensuring parental oversight, the law reduces the risk of misuse of children's personal information on social media and digital platforms. It also imposes accountability on organisations to adopt privacy-by-design measures, strengthen data security practices, and prevent the circulation of harmful or derogatory content involving minors. Thus, while the Personal Data Protection Bill, 2019, laid the conceptual foundation, the current statutory regime under the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023, operationalises these protections, marking a significant step forward in securing children's digital rights and privacy in India.

9.3 Age of Consent

A significant challenge under this framework is determining the appropriate age of consent for data processing. In many cases, children below 18 may engage on social media platforms without parental oversight, complicating privacy protections.

9.4 Role of Social Media Platforms

Social media intermediaries functioning in India are legally bound to adhere to the Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code) Rules, 2021, framed under the Information Technology Act, 2000. These Rules impose due diligence obligations on platforms to ensure a safer digital environment. In particular, intermediaries are required to remove or disable access to unlawful or harmful content, including material that may constitute cyberbullying, within 36 hours of receiving a valid complaint or government notice. A key compliance requirement under these Rules is the appointment of designated officials such as a Grievance Officer, a Nodal Contact Person, and a Chief Compliance Officer (for significant social media intermediaries). The Grievance Officer plays a crucial role in addressing user complaints, including those involving online harassment, defamation, or bullying, and must acknowledge complaints within 24 hours and resolve them within a stipulated timeframe. This mechanism is particularly important in cyberbullying cases, where timely intervention can prevent further psychological harm to victims (Dredge, R. et al., 2014). Additionally, the Rules introduce enhanced responsibilities for “significant social media intermediaries,” including enabling traceability of the originator of certain messages (subject to legal safeguards), deploying automated tools to identify harmful content, and publishing periodic compliance reports. These measures aim to increase accountability and transparency in platform governance. From a broader legal standpoint, these Rules operate alongside provisions of the IT Act such as Sections 66C, 66D, 66E, and 67 series which penalise identity theft, impersonation, privacy violations, and the dissemination of obscene or explicit material. Together, they form a regulatory framework intended to curb online abuse and protect users, especially vulnerable groups like minors. However, despite the existence of this legal structure, enforcement remains uneven. In practice, platforms may delay action, inadequately assess complaints, or fail to prioritise user safety, particularly in cases involving children and adolescents. Concerns have also been raised regarding the lack of transparency, insufficient grievance redressal efficiency, and challenges in balancing user privacy with regulatory compliance. Consequently, while the legal framework is relatively robust on paper, its effectiveness depends significantly on consistent enforcement, platform accountability, and stronger oversight mechanisms.

10. Lacunae in Indian Laws

Certain activities are not considered crimes in India, even though numerous crimes against minors are prohibited. Even though it is not permitted in many other countries, cyberbullying is a major offence in India. That's how sexting operates. Cyberbullying and sexting are not considered serious crimes in India as there is no legal framework in place to penalise these behaviours. While it is against the law to traffic children to use them for sexual exploitation, the law does not expressly address the trafficking of minors to create pornographic or obscene content. (Ovejero, A. et al, 2016) It also makes no mention of cyber grooming, which is another crime that is sadly done against children in our country and has the potential to be fatal. The goal of cyber grooming is to facilitate sexual exploitation.

Both the Information and Technology Act of 2000 and the POCSO Act of 2012 need to be amended.

i. In any written document, graphic representation, audio recording, or portrayal, it is unlawful to encourage or counsel sexual conduct with someone under the age of 18. This is an addition to the POCSO Act of 2012.

ii. In light of this, the IT Act of 2000 was modified to include provisions for disciplinary actions against those who offer pornography to kids and against those who gather, produce, or distribute data on child sexual abuse.

iii. Accountability of organisations receiving actionable intelligence: This would enable law enforcement organisations worldwide to exchange intelligence to ensure investigations, including local police departments.

iv. Speedy legal deterrence through investigation and disposal: Fast-tracked investigation and case resolution, along with a comprehensive definition of child pornography and changes to the POCSO and IT Act, would offer the necessary deterrent.

Given the sharp rise in child-related cybercrimes, this emerging threat requires special attention. In the event of a speedy trial and subsequent prosecution, offenders may be discouraged, both now and in the future. As a result, Indian law does not address every aspect of children's online safety. Comprehensive safeguards for children's online interests, as well as legislation and development, are still needed in this field.

11. Government Initiatives in India: Contemporary Legal Framework

In India, governmental efforts are anchored in a robust and evolving legal framework aimed at addressing cyber-related issues and ensuring digital safety. These initiatives derive their authority from key statutes such as the Information Technology Act, 2000, which provides legal recognition to electronic records and prescribes penalties for cyber offences, along with provisions under the Indian Penal Code that address harassment, defamation, and related misconduct.

To strengthen enforcement and prevention, the government has introduced institutional mechanisms and policy initiatives. The Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MeitY) plays a central role in formulating digital governance policies, while the Indian Cyber Crime Coordination Centre operates under the Ministry of Home Affairs to coordinate efforts in tackling cybercrime nationwide.

Additionally, platforms such as the National Cyber Crime Reporting Portal enable citizens to report online offences, including cyberbullying and harassment, thereby improving access to justice. Awareness campaigns and capacity-building programs have also been initiated to educate users about safe digital practices and legal remedies.

Recent regulatory developments, including the Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code) Rules, 2021, impose obligations on social media intermediaries to ensure accountability, remove unlawful content, and protect users from online harm.

Collectively, these initiatives reflect India's commitment to strengthening its legal and institutional response to cyber threats while promoting a safer and more accountable digital ecosystem.

11.1 The Nirbhaya Funds Scheme

The Government of India introduced a dedicated initiative in 2013 aimed at enhancing the safety and protection of women and children through the **Nirbhaya Fund Scheme**, established in the aftermath of the 2012 Delhi gang rape case. This fund was designed to support projects and schemes focused on improving security infrastructure, emergency response mechanisms, and victim assistance services across the country. One of the key outcomes of this initiative is the **Emergency**

Response Support System (ERSS), developed by the Ministry of Home Affairs. ERSS provides a unified emergency helpline number **112** which enables individuals in distress to access immediate assistance from police, fire services, medical aid, or other emergency response agencies through a single platform. The system integrates technology-driven solutions such as GPS-based location tracking, mobile applications, and state-level control rooms to ensure swift and coordinated responses to emergencies. From a contemporary legal standpoint, the functioning of ERSS and similar safety mechanisms is supported by a broader statutory framework. This includes provisions under the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013, which strengthened laws relating to sexual offences and victim protection, as well as the Information Technology Act, 2000, which addresses cyber-related crimes affecting women and children. Additionally, schemes funded under the Nirbhaya corpus are implemented in coordination with state governments and relevant ministries, ensuring compliance with constitutional mandates relating to the protection of life and personal liberty under Article 21. In recent years, the legal and policy framework has been further reinforced through digital governance initiatives, standard operating procedures for emergency response, and increased accountability mechanisms for law enforcement agencies. Collectively, these measures reflect a more structured and legally grounded approach to ensuring rapid assistance, victim safety, and effective crisis management in India (Kaur, M. et al., 2022).

11.2 Cyber Crime Prevention against Women and Children (CCPWC/CCPWS)

The Cyber Crime Prevention against Women and Children (CCPWC) initiative establishes a coordinated institutional mechanism for addressing online offences, particularly those affecting vulnerable groups such as women and minors. It involves multiple specialised units responsible for receiving and processing cybercrime complaints, conducting investigations, analysing digital evidence, and identifying patterns or suspicious activities linked to cyber offences (Dr. Dalbeer Lal, 2022). The scheme reflects the growing need for a structured and technology-driven response to cyber threats in India.

With an estimated financial outlay of approximately ₹223.198 crores, the programme comprises several key components:

- i. A dedicated online cybercrime reporting portal that enables victims to lodge complaints easily and ensures prompt redressal.
- ii. Establishment of a national-level cyber forensic laboratory to support investigation agencies with advanced digital evidence analysis.
- iii. Capacity-building initiatives, including specialised training programmes for police personnel, judicial officers, and public prosecutors to enhance their competence in handling cyber-related cases.
- iv. Public awareness campaigns aimed at educating citizens about cyber risks, preventive measures, and legal remedies.
- v. Promotion of research and development to strengthen technological capabilities and policy responses in combating cybercrime.

Empirical data highlights the growing reliance on such mechanisms, as more than 3,800 complaints were registered on the official portal (www.cybercrime.gov.in) in 2019 alone, indicating increasing awareness and reporting of cyber offences.

vi. **Present Legal Framework and Basis:** The CCPWC scheme operates within the broader legal framework governing cybercrime in India. The primary legislation is the *Information Technology Act, 2000*, as amended in 2008, which criminalises a wide range of online offences such as identity theft (Section 66C), cheating by impersonation (Section 66D), and violation of privacy (Section 66E). Additionally, Sections 67, 67A, and 67B address the transmission of obscene,

sexually explicit, and child sexual abuse material in electronic form, prescribing stringent penalties. Complementing the IT Act, provisions of the *Indian Penal Code, 1860* (now largely replaced by the *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023*) are also invoked in cases involving cyber harassment, defamation, stalking, and threats. For instance, offences such as online stalking, intimidation, and outraging the modesty of women are addressed under relevant penal provisions. Further, specialised statutes such as the *Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, 2012 (POCSO)* play a critical role in cases involving minors, especially in instances of online exploitation, grooming, or dissemination of child sexual abuse material. Law enforcement agencies also rely on procedural laws like the *Code of Criminal Procedure* (now replaced by the *Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023*) for investigation and prosecution. In addition, the Government of India has strengthened institutional mechanisms through the establishment of the Indian Cyber Crime Coordination Centre (I4C) under the Ministry of Home Affairs, which works in tandem with the CCPWC scheme to ensure coordinated action across states.

Overall, the CCPWC initiative, supported by this comprehensive legal framework, represents a significant step toward safeguarding women and children in the digital space by combining legal enforcement, technological infrastructure, and public awareness.

11.3 Indian Cybercrime Coordination Centre (I4C) scheme

The **Indian Cyber Crime Coordination Centre (I4C)**, set up under the Ministry of Home Affairs, serves as a centralised mechanism to tackle cybercrime in India through a coordinated and comprehensive approach. It aims to prevent the misuse of digital and social media platforms while strengthening the country's capacity to address various forms of cyber offences. I4C facilitates collaboration among law enforcement agencies, forensic experts, academia, and private stakeholders, while also incorporating global best practices and technological advancements. It particularly focuses on issues arising from online platforms, with special attention to protecting women and children from cyber offences. The Centre also promotes awareness among youth about cyber risks such as financial fraud and encourages prompt reporting of such crimes through platforms like the National Cyber Crime Reporting Portal to minimise losses and enable timely action. I4C operates within the framework of the Information Technology Act, 2000 and aligns with other relevant laws such as the *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023*. Although it is not a statutory body, it functions through executive policies and administrative mechanisms to support effective cybercrime prevention and enforcement in India.

12. Cybercrime Reporting Platforms and Helpline Services

12.1 National cybercrime reporting portal

The Government of India provides an online complaint mechanism through the **National Cyber Crime Reporting Portal (NCCRP)**, allowing victims, particularly women and children, to report instances of online harassment or abuse. Complaints submitted on the platform are processed promptly, often with the support of local police authorities to ensure timely action. In comparison to conventional offline procedures, technology-driven reporting systems enable faster and more efficient handling of cybercrime complaints. The portal serves as a centralised platform for registering cyber offences across the country, offering victims and complainants convenient access to cybercrime cells as well as relevant information and resources. Alternatively, victims may also choose to lodge complaints directly at their nearest cybercrime cell instead of using the online system. The portal further provides state-wise details of nodal cyber cell officers, along with contact information and official

email IDs of grievance officers, thereby enhancing accessibility and coordination in addressing cyber offences (Sanjeev Kumar & Deeksha, 2021).

12.2 Anti-bullying or cyberbullying laws in India for schools and colleges

In response to the significant rise in bullying, particularly in residential and boarding schools in India, the Ministry of Human Resource Development (now the Ministry of Education India) initiated the formation of anti-ragging committees. These bodies are responsible for monitoring student conduct and taking disciplinary action against those involved in such behaviour. In cases of severe misconduct, the penalties may extend to suspension or even expulsion (rustication) from the institution. At the higher education level, the University Grants Commission (UGC) has established comprehensive anti-ragging regulations applicable to colleges and universities. These guidelines are designed to curb the incidence of ragging by prescribing preventive measures, awareness initiatives, and strict punitive actions, thereby promoting a safer academic environment.

13. Judicial Precedents Regarding Cyberbullying

The intensity and effects of cyberbullying have been brought to light in India via several historical examples. These instances have raised awareness of the problem and helped to shape the legislation and regulations intended to stop cyberbullying. Among the most noteworthy landmark cases are the following:

Shreya Singhal v. Union of India, (2015) 5 SCC 1 (India): In this landmark judgment, the Supreme Court of India struck down Section 66A of the Information Technology Act, 2000, holding that the provision was vague, overbroad, and violative of the constitutional guarantee of freedom of speech and expression under Article 19(1)(a). While the decision primarily concerned online speech, it remains significant in cyberbullying jurisprudence because it clarified the limits of governmental regulation of online communications and established principles regarding intermediary liability. The Court further held that online platforms could be required to remove content only pursuant to a court order or a government directive issued in accordance with law. This decision continues to influence debates concerning the regulation of harmful online conduct, including cyberbullying.

Justice K. S. Puttaswamy (Retd.) v. Union of India, (2017) 10 SCC 1 (India): The nine-judge constitutional bench unanimously recognised the right to privacy as a fundamental right under Article 21 of the Constitution of India. The judgment has profound implications for children in digital spaces because it established informational privacy, data protection, and autonomy as constitutional values. The principles articulated in this case provide the legal foundation for protecting children against cyberbullying, online surveillance, identity theft, doxing, and unauthorised disclosure of personal information.

State of Tamil Nadu v. Suhas Katti, C.C. No. 4680 of 2004 (Chief Metropolitan Magistrate, Egmore, Chennai, 2004): Widely regarded as India's first successful cybercrime conviction, the case involved persistent online harassment, defamatory postings, and obscene messages directed toward a woman through electronic platforms. The accused was convicted under the provisions of the Information Technology Act and the Indian Penal Code. The judgment demonstrated that online harassment and digital abuse could attract criminal liability and set an early precedent for addressing cyberbullying-like conduct in India.

Avnish Bajaj v. State (NCT of Delhi), 150 (2008) DLT 769 (India): Arising from the infamous "Bazee.com" case, the Delhi High Court examined intermediary liability for unlawful content disseminated through online platforms. Although the matter concerned obscene content rather than cyberbullying, the judgment significantly contributed to the development of intermediary responsibility in

cyberspace. The case remains relevant when discussing the obligations of digital platforms to prevent harmful online behaviour affecting children.

S. Krishna Sinha v. State of Bihar, 2019 SCC OnLine Pat 1728.: The Court emphasised that cyber harassment and online intimidation can have severe psychological effects on victims and recognised the growing need for effective legal intervention in cyberspace. The decision highlighted the importance of balancing freedom of expression with protection against online abuse and harassment.

Doe v. MySpace, Inc., 528 F.3d 413 (5th Cir. 2008): In this case, the parents of a minor argued that the social networking platform failed to protect children from online predators adequately. Although the court ultimately granted the platform immunity under Section 230 of the Communications Decency Act, the case sparked significant debate about social media platforms' responsibilities for safeguarding children online and preventing digital victimisation.

Kowalski v. Berkeley County Schools, 652 F.3d 565 (4th Cir. 2011): A student created a webpage ridiculing and harassing a fellow student. The court upheld disciplinary action taken by the school, holding that schools may intervene when online conduct substantially disrupts the educational environment or infringes upon the rights of other students. This decision is particularly important for understanding the role of educational institutions in combating cyberbullying.

J.S. ex-rel. Snyder v. Blue Mountain School District, 650 F.3d 915 (3d Cir. 2011): The case involved a student who created a fake online profile of a school principal. The court examined the extent to which schools may regulate off-campus online speech. Although the student's discipline was overturned, the judgment established important standards concerning the relationship between digital expression, school authority, and student rights in cyberspace.

R v. Elliott, 2016 ONCJ 35 (Can.): This Canadian case addressed allegations of repeated online harassment through social media communications. The proceedings generated extensive discussion regarding cyberbullying, freedom of expression, and criminal liability for persistent online abuse. It remains a leading comparative authority concerning cyber harassment and digital victimisation.

A.B. v. Bragg Communications Inc., 2012 SCC 46 (Can.): A teenage victim sought disclosure of the identity of an anonymous individual who had created a fake Facebook profile designed to humiliate her. The Supreme Court of Canada permitted the victim to proceed anonymously, recognising the serious harms associated with cyberbullying and the need to protect child victims from further psychological injury. The judgment is internationally recognised as a leading authority on protecting children from online harassment.

14. Conclusions and Suggestions

In an increasingly interconnected digital society, cyberbullying has emerged as a significant socio-legal challenge that necessitates comprehensive and multidimensional responses extending beyond conventional legal remedies. In India, the prevalence of cyberbullying is particularly alarming among children and adolescents, who constitute one of the most vulnerable groups of internet users. The frequency of cyberbullying incidents continues to increase with the rapid expansion of digital technologies, social media platforms, and internet accessibility. Individuals who engage with online platforms are often exposed to various forms of cyber harassment, including intimidation, threats, defamation, impersonation, and other abusive conduct. Such experiences can have profound psychological consequences, adversely affecting victims' mental health, self-esteem, confidence, and overall well-being. Victims of cyberbullying frequently begin to question their abilities, personal worth, and social acceptance (Rufa Mitsu et al., 2022).

The adverse consequences of cyberbullying are not confined to victims alone. Research indicates that individuals who engage in cyberbullying may also experience social isolation, behavioural difficulties, and psychological distress, potentially contributing to long-term mental health concerns, including depression. Despite the growing magnitude of the problem, India does not currently possess a dedicated statutory framework specifically addressing cyberbullying. Nevertheless, several provisions of the Information Technology Act, 2000, and the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023 (formerly the Indian Penal Code, 1860) provide legal recourse against conduct commonly associated with cyberbullying. However, the anonymous nature of online interactions often creates significant challenges for law enforcement agencies in identifying and prosecuting offenders.

Considering the scale of internet usage and the demographic diversity of India, there is a pressing need for legislative reforms that explicitly recognize and address cyberbullying as a distinct offence. Simultaneously, governmental authorities, educational institutions, civil society organisations, and private stakeholders should collaborate to conduct awareness campaigns, digital literacy programmes, webinars, and community outreach initiatives aimed at educating the public regarding online risks and responsible digital behaviour. Particular attention must be given to equipping children, adolescents, and young adults with the skills necessary to navigate digital environments safely and responsibly.

As India continues its rapid digital transformation, addressing cyberbullying must remain a policy priority. Existing legal frameworks should be periodically reviewed and interpreted in light of evolving technological realities and emerging forms of online harm. Promoting digital literacy, responsible online conduct, and ethical engagement in virtual spaces is essential for creating a safer and more inclusive digital environment (Ritu Chhabra et al., 2020). Furthermore, the widespread use of smartphones and internet-enabled devices across all age groups necessitates greater oversight, awareness, and digital responsibility. The intersection of cyberbullying with related phenomena such as online hate speech, trolling, doxing, cyberstalking, and the dissemination of misinformation further underscores the need for robust legislative measures, educational interventions, and effective platform governance mechanisms. A coordinated approach involving law, education, technology, and community participation is therefore indispensable to mitigating online harm and ensuring the protection of digital rights.

14.1. Strategies for Preventing and Addressing Cyberbullying

Cyberbullying has emerged as a serious socio-legal concern in the digital age, particularly affecting students, adolescents, and young internet users. Effective prevention and intervention require a collaborative framework involving students, parents, educators, counsellors, policymakers, and law enforcement authorities. Such efforts must be supported by a robust legal and institutional framework capable of addressing both the technological and psychological dimensions of cyberbullying.

14.1.1. Measures Students Can Adopt

Students play a crucial role in protecting themselves from cyberbullying and other forms of online victimisation. They should exercise caution when sharing personal information, including phone numbers, passwords, addresses, photographs, and other sensitive data, particularly with unknown or unverified individuals. Regularly updating passwords, usernames, and privacy settings is essential for maintaining digital security and reducing vulnerability to cyber threats. Students should also utilise available technological safeguards by blocking individuals or accounts that engage in abusive, threatening, or harassing behaviour. Importantly, victims should avoid responding to hostile communications, as engagement may escalate the situation. Instead, such messages, screenshots, emails, and online interactions should be preserved as evidence for reporting and legal purposes.

Familiarity with available reporting mechanisms, including the National Cyber Crime Reporting Portal and institutional grievance redressal systems, is equally important to ensure timely intervention and legal recourse.

14.1.2. Role of Parents in Combating Cyberbullying

Parents constitute the first line of protection against online harm and play a critical role in fostering safe digital practices among children. They should monitor and regulate the duration and nature of their children's online activities while ensuring that internet use occurs within a secure and supervised environment. Equally important is the establishment of open and trust-based communication regarding internet safety, online privacy, and the risks associated with cyberbullying. Parents should educate children about responsible digital citizenship, the implications of digital footprints, privacy protection, and the importance of maintaining confidentiality online. Encouraging open dialogue enables children to report incidents of cyberbullying without fear of punishment, embarrassment, or social stigma, thereby facilitating early intervention and support.

14.1.3. Role of Counsellors and Institutional Support Systems

School counsellors, psychologists, and mental health professionals play a vital role in addressing the emotional, psychological, and social consequences of cyberbullying. Through awareness programmes and counselling interventions, they can educate students regarding the nature, consequences, and coping mechanisms associated with cyberbullying.

Key institutional strategies include:

- Developing and implementing comprehensive school policies specifically addressing cyberbullying and related online misconduct.
- Conducting classroom guidance programmes, peer-support initiatives, and awareness campaigns to promote empathy, inclusion, and collective responsibility.
- Providing individual counselling, psychological support, and rehabilitation services to victims.
- Organising workshops, consultations, and training programmes for students, teachers, and parents aimed at enhancing resilience, emotional intelligence, and digital literacy.

Such interventions contribute significantly to the early identification, prevention, and effective management of cyberbullying incidents.

14.1.4. Responsibilities of Educators and Schools

Educational institutions bear a significant responsibility in creating safe, inclusive, and respectful digital learning environments. Schools should establish clear codes of conduct and disciplinary policies addressing cyberbullying and ensure that students are fully aware of the consequences associated with online misconduct. Educators should actively promote a positive school culture grounded in respect, empathy, and responsible digital engagement. Regular professional development programmes focusing on cyber safety, digital ethics, emerging online threats, and technological developments should be conducted to enhance teachers' capacity to identify and address cyberbullying effectively. Furthermore, integrating digital citizenship, cyber ethics, and online safety education into school curricula can serve as a proactive mechanism for preventing cyberbullying and promoting responsible internet use.

14.1.5. Legal Position in India

Although India does not currently have a standalone legislation exclusively addressing cyberbullying, several provisions under existing statutory frameworks provide legal remedies against cyberbullying-related conduct.

- i. The Information Technology Act, 2000, establishes the principal legal framework governing cyber offences in India. Sections 66C (identity theft), 66D (cheating by personation using computer resources), and 66E (violation of privacy) are frequently invoked in cases involving cyberbullying and online harassment.
- ii. Sections 67, 67A, and 67B of the Information Technology Act address the publication and transmission of obscene, sexually explicit, and child sexual abuse material, including offences involving minors.
- iii. Under the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023 (formerly the Indian Penal Code, 1860), provisions relating to stalking, criminal intimidation, defamation, harassment through anonymous communication, and offences affecting the dignity and privacy of individuals may be applied depending upon the nature of the cyberbullying conduct.
- iv. It is noteworthy that Section 66A of the Information Technology Act, which was previously invoked in relation to online communications, was declared unconstitutional by the Supreme Court of India in *Shreya Singhal v. Union of India* on the ground that it violated the constitutional guarantee of freedom of speech and expression.

Victims may seek redress through local cybercrime police stations, specialised cybercrime cells, or the National Cyber Crime Reporting Portal. Data published by the National Crime Records Bureau indicate a consistent increase in cybercrime cases over the past decade, with a substantial proportion involving online harassment, identity theft, cyberstalking, and social media abuse. Women and minors remain particularly vulnerable to such offences, many of which continue to go unreported due to social stigma, fear of retaliation, and limited awareness of available legal remedies. International studies similarly reveal that a significant proportion of adolescents experience some form of cyberbullying during their lives, highlighting the urgent need for preventive education, institutional safeguards, and effective enforcement mechanisms.

Accordingly, addressing cyberbullying requires a holistic and multidisciplinary strategy that combines individual vigilance, parental involvement, educational responsibility, psychological support, technological safeguards, and effective legal enforcement. Strengthening digital literacy, improving reporting and grievance redressal mechanisms, promoting responsible online behaviour, and enhancing awareness regarding digital rights and responsibilities are essential steps toward creating a safer, more secure, and more inclusive digital environment for all users.

References

- Batra, S. (2020). A study of bullying and cyberbullying and the legal angle. *Journal of Legal Studies and Research*, 6(5), 127–130.
- Shivashankar, B. S., Rajan, A., & Saveetha School of Law. (2018). A critical analysis of cyberbullying in India with special reference to bullying in college. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 119(17), 1811–1822.
- Dredge, R., Gleeson, J., & de la Piedad García, X. (2014). Cyberbullying in social networking sites: An adolescent victim's perspective. *Computers in Human Behaviour*, 36, 13–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.03.036>
- Lal, D. (2022). Protecting the child from the evil effects of the digital age. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*.
- Bhadury, S. (2022). Child pornography in India: Issues and challenges. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*.
- Gamefski, N., & Kraaij, V. (2014). Bully victimisation and emotional problems in adolescents: Moderation by specific cognitive coping strategies? *Journal of Adolescence*, 37(7), 1153–1160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2014.07.005>

- Hoff, D. L., & Mitchell, S. N. (2009). Cyberbullying: Causes, effects, and remedies. *Journal of Educational Administration, 47*(5), 652–665. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09578230910981107>
- Thapa, J. (2024). The protection of children from cyber crimes in India. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research, 6*(3).
- Kapoor, V. (2024). What you need to know about cyberbullying and its legal remedies. *iPleaders*. <https://blog.iplayers.in>
- Kaur, M., & Saini, M. (2022). Indian government initiatives on cyberbullying. *Education and Information Technologies, 28*(1), 581–615.
- Khudhair, N. S. (2021). Cyberbullying: A critical analysis. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government, 27*(3).
- Mittal, S. (2024). Legal challenges of cyberbullying and online harassment. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research, 6*(2), 1–3.
- Rahul, Choudhary, S., & Azhari, M. (2022). Crime against children in cyberspace in India. *Global Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*.
- Pooja, & Vats, A. (2023). The growing threat of cyberbullying in India. *International Journal of Educational Research and Educational Development (IJERED)*.
- Akshita, N., et al. (2023). Right to privacy of children over the internet. *Supremo Amicus, 32*.
- National Commission for Protection of Child Rights. (2021). *Preventing bullying and cyberbullying: Guidelines for schools*. Government of India.
- National Crime Records Bureau. (2020). *Crime in India 2019* (Vol. 1). Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India.
- Ovejero, A., et al. (2016). *Cyberbullying: Definitions and facts*.
- Pallathadka, H., et al. (2021). Cyberbullying vis-à-vis emotional unrest. *Journal of Cardiovascular Disease Research, 12*(2), 541–542.
- Pandey, C. (2023). Cyberbullying in India: A growing concern. *Times of India Blog*.
- Pathak, V. K., et al. (2024). Prevalence and factors associated with cyberbullying. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry, 66*(5), 449–456.
- Press Information Bureau. (n.d.). *Cybercrime prevention against women and children*. Government of India. <https://pib.gov.in>
- Raj, A. (2024). Cyberbullying and related laws in India. *International Journal of Novel Research and Development (IJNRD)*.
- Refai, S. A., & Bhat, S. M. (2024). Cyberbullying: Human rights perspective. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*.
- Chhabra, R., & Singh, S. K. (2020). *Rights of children in the cyber world*.
- Mitsu, R., & Dawood, E. (2022). *Cyberbullying: An overview*.
- Kumar, S., & Deeksha. (2021). *Crime against children in the cyber world*.
- Kumar, S., & Deeksha. (2021). *Cybercrime reporting and legal mechanisms in India*.
- Kumar, S., & Deeksha. (2021). *Cybercrime against women in India: A legal analysis*.
- Errakot, S., & VK, R. (2023). Cyberbullying: A need for separate provision in Indian law. *GLS Law Journal, 5*(1).
- Sharma, D., et al. (2022). *Evidence to action: Research and policy implications in India*. Pressbooks.
- Sharma, S. (2023). *Child cyber abuse: Analytical study*. ICFAI University, Dehradun.
- Gautam, S., & Sharma, S. (2023). Cyberbullying: Repercussions and strategies. *Research Communication, 1*(2), 172–178.
- TNN. (2024). Child cybercrime surges 32%: NCRB report.
- Thomas, S., & Pandey, D.-M. K. (2023). Cyberbullying in India: Psycho-legal prevention. *Indian Journal of Psychology*.
- Tripathi, S., et al. (2011). Cyberbullying and the law. *Law Mantra*.
- Zhu, C., et al. (2021). Cyberbullying among adolescents and children: A comprehensive review. *Frontiers in Public Health, 9*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.634909>